

Distinction between the reactivity of phosphorus ylide vs sulfur ylide with the carbonyl compounds : Simplicity and logic

Suchandra Chakraborty^a, Kaushik Basu^b and Chandan Saha^{*a}

^aDepartment of Clinical and Experimental Pharmacology, School of Tropical Medicine, Kolkata-700 073, India

E-mail : cskatichandan@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, St. Paul's Cathedral Mission College, Kolkata-700 009, India

Abstract : Wittig olefination and Corey-Chaykovsky epoxidation of carbonyl compounds are well-documented classical and synthetically useful name reactions which are taught in great details in both undergraduate and post-graduate curricula of organic chemistry. Whilst similar reagents (a phosphorus ylide in Wittig olefination and a sulfur ylide in Corey-Chaykovsky epoxidation) and same substrate (a carbonyl compound) are deployed in both reactions, their outcome is strikingly different. Yet any discussion of reasons behind this differential behavior is conspicuously absent in almost all of the textbooks and the issue remains a perpetual source of confusion among students. In this article an attempt has been made to shed light on this problem and dispel those confusions through qualitative discussion of the theories and experimental results concerning the mechanistic details of these reactions.

Introduction

Ylides emerged for the first time as early as the 1900s, but these structurally unique compounds became accredited as members of valuable synthetic reagents only after the establishment of Wittig reaction in 1953¹. Since then, the chemistry of ylides sprang up rapidly and these became authoritative and versatile synthetic reagents to organic chemists. Ylides are a very special class of compounds in which two opposite charges are in closest propinquity and it can be regarded as an exceptional carbanion with an adjoining positively charged heteroatom with octet of electrons and

accordingly these serve the purpose of nucleophilic synthones. In modern synthetic organic chemistry phosphorus and sulfur ylides have laid their giant imprints as significant reagents. In Wittig^{1,2}, Wittig-Horner³ and Horner-Wadsworth-Emmons⁴ olefination reactions phosphorus ylides and allied phosphoryl-stabilized carbanions are employed whereas sulfur ylides are distinguished as crucial reagents for the syntheses of three-membered carbo- and heterocyclic rings, viz. Corey-Chaykovsky reaction⁵.

Wittig reaction : Phosphorus ylide in action

Wittig reaction is one of the most suitable techniques available for the synthesis of C=C double bonds with high degree of stereoselectivity. The reaction has found extreme application in various synthetic schemes leading to the construction of a variety of structural motifs and numerous synthetic targets. To accomplish Wittig reaction, initially Wittig reagent, a phosphorus ylide is incurred by treating a primary or secondary alkyl halide with triphenylphosphine, Ph₃P to achieve phosphonium salt via S_N2 followed by the treatment with a strong base such as PhLi in dry THF or *n*-BuLi in dry ether (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Formation of Wittig reagent.

In the next step, when Wittig reagent is permitted to interact with a carbonyl compound an oxaphosphetane intermediate is formed through a concerted [2+2] cycloaddition having a transition state in which the extent of C—C bond formation exceeds that of the formation of P—O bond⁶. The resulting oxaphosphetane is then partitioned off into the olefin and triphenyl phosphine oxide (Scheme 2) via a reverse [2+2] cycloaddition.

The oxaphosphetane intermediate formation from nonstabilised ylide is in general a nonreversible step⁷. However, the critical character of this

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Scheme 2. Wittig reaction to form alkenes.

reaction is its stereoselectivity, viz. with nonstabilized ylide *cis*-olefin is obtained preferentially whereas *trans*-olefin with stabilized ylide⁸. As a result, the reaction can be predicted in accordance with Scheme 3.

Scheme 3. Nonstabilised ylide leads to *cis*-olefin and stabilised ylide leads to *trans*-olefin.

To explain the stereoselectivity in such olefination reaction, one can depict the course of the reaction as illustrated in Scheme 4⁹.

Scheme 4. Wittig reaction via oxephosphatane intermediate and its *syn*-stereoselectivity.

The reaction commences with a concerted [2+2] cycloaddition in compliance with the concept of conservation of orbital symmetry where the carbonyl group and the nonstabilised ylide approach orthogonally to achieve the oxaphosphetane intermediate (3), keeping the larger substituents apart and oxygen occupying the apical position. This intermediate (3) then experiences Berry pseudorotation to isomerize to the intermediate (4) where oxygen and carbon centers switch over their positions so that carbon now occupies the apical position and subsequent reverse [2+2] cycloaddition leads to *cis*-alkene. According to the concept of the conservation of orbital symmetry the $[\pi^2_s + \pi^2_s]$ cycloaddition is symmetry forbidden under thermal condition as the HOMO/LUMO combination between two components leads to an antibonding interaction at one end, whereas thermal $[\pi^2_s + \pi^2_a]$ cycloaddition is symmetry allowed but geometrically disabled. Now this geometrical incapability can be alleviated if the two π -systems approach orthogonally to each other. Fig. 1 shows how these two π -systems i.e. HOMO of phosphorus ylide and LUMO of the carbonyl group interact through this new and potentially fruitful orthogonal alignment to form the oxaphosphetane intermediate in Wittig reaction¹⁰.

Fig. 1. Interactions between the HOMO of phosphorus ylide and LUMO of carbonyl compound.

Here, for thermally allowed [2+2] cycloaddition, there are two primary bonding interactions between HOMO of the ylide (π^2s) with that of the LUMO of the carbonyl compounds (π^2a) but there are two secondary antibonding interactions between them which is however, counterbalanced by the two other secondary bonding interactions between an extra *p* orbital (due to the *sp* hybridisation of oxygen in C=O) of the oxygen atom with the HOMO of the ylide. Obviously then, all in all there are four bonding interactions and two antibondings. As a result, the proportionality is in favor of oxaphosphetane formation via [$\pi^2s + \pi^2a$] cycloaddition¹⁰ through bonding interactions.

Vedejs¹¹ characterized for the first time the oxaphosphetane intermediate unambiguously through spectroscopic studies. It was isolated as well as characterized by X-ray diffraction¹². Bestmann *et al.* through a unique study have shown an intermediary of the pentacoordinated phosphorus, **3**, in which the oxygen engages the apical position and this is in harmony with the Muetterties apicophilicity rules. They have also indicated that a pseudorotation is likely to occur with considerable certainty so that the oxygen and carbon centers exchange their positions (**3** into **4**)¹³. In a trigonal-bipyramidal hypervalent phosphorus system¹⁴ the apical bonds are weaker than the equatorial ones and thus through pseudorotation the equatorial P—C bond becomes weaker apical bond. This eases the formation of the *cis*-olefin and phosphine oxide via reverse [2+2] cycloaddition (where the C—C bond formation exceeds the P—O bond formation) from the new oxaphosphetane **4**, which is in equilibrium with **3** (Scheme 4).

When stabilized ylide is allowed to interact with carbonyl compounds *trans*-alkene results. In this case, it is proposed that the extra stability of the ylide makes the oxaphosphetane formation step reversible (Scheme 5).

In the case of stabilized ylide, stereoselectivity is, therefore, no longer a matter of kinetics but is controlled by thermodynamics. Thus the initially formed less stable *cis*-oxaphosphetane is essentially a kinetically controlled diastereomer, having a transition state where the two bulky groups far apart during orthogonal alignment for [2+2] cycloaddition and so it forms at a faster rate. However, this less stable oxaphosphetane from stabilized ylide follows a reverse course to yield the starting materials which recombines to

Scheme 5. Rationale for the formation of *trans*-olefin from stabilised ylide.

afford thermodynamically more stable *trans*-oxaphosphetane diastereomer (as two bulky groups are on the opposite sides of the ring) via a less stable transition state where two bulky groups are in close proximity during [2+2] cycloaddition (Fig. 2)^{7c,10}.

Undoubtedly, from the above study it can be speculated that kinetically formed *cis*-oxaphosphetane from stabilised ylide follows the reverse course at a faster rate than that of the formation of *cis*-alkene. At the same time, the rate of the formation of *cis*-alkene from *cis*-oxaphosphetane is significantly slower than the rate of formation of *trans*-alkene from *trans*-oxaphosphetane and it can be counted simply by considering steric factors in their respective transition states. The *anti* diastereoisomer (9) is, therefore, 'siphoned off' to give *trans*-alkene more rapidly than the *syn* diastereoisomer (4) to give *cis*-alkene (Scheme 6) from equilibration of the two

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Fig. 2. Transition states during the formation of oxaphosphetane intermediates.

Scheme 6. Depending on the nature of the ylides *cis*- or *trans*-alkene is formed.

oxaphosphetane diastereomers via starting material and thus the equilibrium shifts irreversibly towards *trans*-alkene in case of stabilised ylides¹⁰.

Thus we do expect the following energy profile diagram for the *trans*-alkene formation from stabilised ylide (Fig. 3).

Corey-Chaykovsky reaction : Sulfur ylide in action

In organic synthesis sulfur ylides represent a formidable class of re-

Fig. 3. Energy profile diagram for the formation of *trans*-alkene from stabilised ylide.

agents. Ingold and Jessop first reported the isolation of a sulfur ylide in 1930¹⁵. However, systematic studies on sulfur ylides were initiated only in the 1960s through the elegant works of E. J. Corey. In modern synthetic organic chemistry the sulfur ylides were distinguished as useful reagents to obtain three-membered carbo- and heterocycles rings via the Corey-Chaykovsky reaction⁵. Johnson *et al.*¹⁶ suggested that Corey-Chaykovsky reaction initiates through a nucleophilic attack of the sulfur ylide on the carbonyl carbon to form a *trans*-betaine intermediate, **11** which is then involved in an intramolecular S_N2 attack at the carbon, in which the oxygen

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acts as the nucleophile and the sulfide as the nucleofuge (Scheme 7) to achieve an oxirane.

Scheme 7. Formation of epoxide with sulfur ylide.

This mechanism was confirmed through a number of studies such as the synthesis of oxirane by deprotonation¹⁷ of the conjugated acid of a betaine. In addition the existence of a betaine intermediate¹⁸ is supported by the fact that an inverse ring opening reaction occurs when some oxiranes are treated with sulfides to yield stabilized sulfur ylides and ketones. The same type mechanistic details are applicable to all sulfur ylide derivatives⁵ such as sulfinyl, sulfonyl-stabilized carbanions, sulfoxides, etc.

Reasons for the difference in behavior between phosphorus and sulfur ylides

The direct contrast between the Wittig reaction that results into the formation of olefinic product and the Corey-Chaykovsky reaction which yields an oxirane is a point of interest. The question is how does the reactivity of a phosphorus ylide differ from that of a sulfur ylide? Understanding the details¹⁹ of the difference in reactivities of the respective ylides mainly come from the theoretical studies by Volatron *et al.*⁹.

The above contrast may be justified qualitatively considering the thermodynamic and kinetic factors. From the thermodynamic point of view, both reactions, Wittig and Corey-Chaykovsky are estimated to be more exothermic⁹ for both ylides in preference to their corresponding alternatives. The higher bond energy of the P-O bond with respect to the S-O bond dictates that with phosphorus ylide, the formation of phosphine oxide and alkene is more exothermic (~49 kcal/mol) than that of oxirane and phosphine (~35 kcal/mol) whereas the reverse thermodynamic conclusion is reached for sulfur ylide, as the formation of oxirane and sulfide (~63 kcal/mol) is preferential over that of sulfoxide and alkene (~24 kcal/mol).

This reversal in thermodynamic preferences is ascribed to the smaller oxo affinity of sulfides compared to that of phosphines. The differential oxo affinity may be attributed due to destabilization through l.p.-l.p. repulsion between the sulfur and oxygen in sulfoxide which is replaced by the smaller b.p-l.p. repulsion between P and O-atom in phosphine oxide.

It is worthwhile to mention that with sulfur ylides no traces of Wittig products have even been isolated. This surprising fact indicates that it is the high time to take a close look on the kinetics of both the reactions, Wittig and Corey-Chaykovsky. The kinetic factors for the Wittig reaction and for the Corey-Chaykovsky reaction have been studied by means of *ab initio* calculations⁹. These calculations suggest that Wittig reaction goes forward via the intermediate formation of oxaphosphetane (**3**) with a lower energy of activation in comparison to the reaction in Corey-Chaykovsky fashion through the transition state TS_{P_1} (Fig. 4). This first formed oxaphosphetane **3** with the oxygen at the apical position lies at well energy valley. It undergoes a Berry pseudorotation, rather turnstile rotation, to form another less stable isomeric oxaphosphetane (**4**) with the oxygen at the equatorial position. This oxaphosphetane (**4**) requires somewhat lower energy of activation through the transition state TS_{P_2} to go to the final products, alkene and phosphine oxide.

Now here the two transition states TS_{P_1} and TS_{P_2} are planar having four membered rings in which bonds are partially formed and broken. In TS_{P_1} the oxygen engages the pseudoapical position of a distorted trigonal bipyramid. Conversely, in TS_{P_2} the ylide carbon leaving the phosphorus occupies the apical site of a regular trigonal bipyramid. Since the apical bond of a trigonal bipyramid is weaker than equatorial one, incoming or leaving group must have to occupy the apical site. As the energy of the second transition state TS_{P_2} is below that of the reactants vide Fig. 4, the system preferentially goes forward to form the olefin and phosphine oxide rather than to follow the reverse course.

In the light of the *ab initio* calculations, let us take a close look on kinetics of Corey-Chakovosky reaction. If sulfur ylide has to react with carbonyl compound in a manner similar to that of phosphorus ylide then an intermediate **12** (Fig. 5) is to be formed with a monotonous decrease in

Fig. 4. Energy profile diagram for phosphorus ylide.

energy without any transition state. This intermediate **12** should be geometrically analogous to **3** with oxygen at the apical position of the sulfur and the lone pair on sulfur at the equatorial site of the pseudo trigonal bipyramid. In addition, it may be mentioned that no oxathietane has been structurally characterized yet. However, sulfuranes having common features with oxathietane have been synthesized and isolated with highly electronegative groups at the apical sites only²⁰. In addition, when sulfur – circumvented by five electron pairs, one of them being non-bonding – replaces phosphorus, a similar pseudorotation is impeded by a high energy barrier. Therefore, in contrast to the phosphorus case, the transformation of the sulfur ylide and carbonyl compound into the Wittig like products through the intermediate **12** will have to proceed via a high energy transition state TS_{S_1} .

Fig. 5. Energy profile diagram for sulfur ylide.

In TS_{P₂} where the carbon is already at the apical site, the cleavage of the P—C bond is encouraged. Necessarily then, the essential point about the transition state TS_{S₁} is that the ylide carbon must have to occupy the apical position while the oxygen is at equatorial site i.e. one must have to concede that a pseudorotation has finally occurred at the sulfur and thus theoretical calculation suggests that it only appears at the TS_{S₁} point on the potential energy surface. This state of affairs is highly unfavorable for the sulfur system compared to the phosphorus one. Whatever relative energies are required to cleave an S—C and a P—C bond from their corresponding four-membered ring intermediates, one must have to sum up with it, the energy desirable to bring the carbon at the apical site. Since it costs much more in the case of sulfur than that in the case of phosphorus, Wittig type reaction is strongly forbidden with the sulfur. It has been estimated that the activa-

tion energy for the reaction following the Wittig fashion is considerably higher in the case of sulfur (~ 38 kcal/mol) than in the case of phosphorus (~ 26 kcal/mol). This is the step that differentiates the reactivity of the two ylides and prevents the sulfur ylide to undergo reaction in Wittig fashion.

On the other hand, in case of sulfur ylides, the formation of oxiranes and sulphides via betaine intermediate is associated with a lower energy of activation via the transition state TS_{S_2} (Fig. 5). This can be explained by considering the facts that first, the sulfur ylide is more reactive than the phosphorus ylide as a nucleophile, which aids the addition step for sulfur (activation energy found to be ~ 10 kcal/mol in the case of sulfur and estimated to be ~ 12 kcal/mol in the case of phosphorus). And second, the nucleofugality of a sulfide is higher than that of a phosphine, which facilitates the intramolecular S_N2 reaction for sulfur. The Corey-Chakovsky reaction thus proceeds more easily in preference over Wittig type reaction for sulfur ylides. This discussion will be incomplete without considering the reaction of phosphorus ylide with carbonyl compound in Corey-Chakovsky fashion. In the case of the phosphorus ylide, it is estimated that the activation energy is ~ 5 kcal/mol for the reaction in Wittig fashion whereas that is ~ 25 kcal/mol for the Corey-Chaykovsky type reaction, due to the lower reactivity of phosphorus ylide and poor nucleofugality of phosphine (Fig. 4).

Conclusion

After this critical discussion it may be concluded that the success of Wittig reaction between carbonyl compound and phosphorus ylide over that of sulfur ylide is due to the ease with which the oxygen can attain at the equatorial site and the carbon at the apical site in their corresponding four-membered intermediates. This interchange of groups has been calculated to be easier in the case of phosphorus but very difficult in the case of sulfur. Again, the higher bond energy of P–O bond than that of S–O bond thermodynamically favors phosphorus ylide to react with carbonyl compound to form an olefin via Wittig reaction. Similarly from the thermodynamic point of view sulfur ylides react with carbonyl compounds in favor of Corey-Chaykovsky reaction to yield oxiranes.

In this discussion so far, it is concluded that Wittig reaction proceeds via the oxaphosphetane intermediate through [2+2] cycloaddition and that leads to *cis*-olefin whereas Corey-Chaykovsky reaction proceeds through betaine intermediate to oxirane. However, it must be mentioned that a dramatic change in stereoselectivity in Wittig reaction was observed in presence of ionic salts where a *trans*-olefin results. It is supposed that in the presence of lithium halides, the oxaphosphetane intermediates can be cleaved into betaine intermediates, which may then isomerize by additional base before they cyclize, forming the thermodynamically more stable *trans*-oxaphosphetanes, which finally yield the *trans*-olefins selectively (Scheme 8).

Scheme 8. Betaine intermediate formation in presence of lithium halide.

As a result, the formation of betaine intermediate during Wittig reaction can't be ruled out completely. In this connection it may be mentioned further that the concept of the formation of betaine intermediate during the conversion of *cis*- to *trans*-olefine and vice-versa through the epoxidation of an alkene followed by the treatment with triphenyl phosphine is well recognized.

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